

QUIZ**LAST NAME: GERALD****FIRST NAME: WOMANIALA****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: SIX****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. An academic essay aims to persuade readers of an idea based on?

- Evidence¹**
- Length of the essay in terms of pages
- Speciality of the researcher of the idea
- The idea at stake

2. As far as essay writing is concerned, the first draft should include?

- Introduction, body and conclusion²**
- Introduction alone
- Body and conclusion alone

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack* (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 1.

² Ibid.

- Two relevant paragraphs
- 3. When writing papers, one of the essential things the writer should do is avoid plagiarism. Plagiarism therefore is?**
- An Art of good essay writing
- Summarising the findings of your essay
- Good researching habits and thorough presentation
- A situation where the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information³**
- 4. When working with in-text citations, what order of information should writers of academic papers observe?**
- Name of author, year of book publication and page number⁴**
- Page number and the course code
- Year of book publication and bibliography
- Only the authors last name will suffice
- 5. Three kinds of questions that researchers usually ask are?**
- Conceptual, practical and applied questions⁵**
- Logical and paper related
- Three dimensional questions

³ Ibid., 5.

⁴ Ibid., 11.

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (8th Ed) (London: The University of Chicago Press, 2013), 16.

- Your age, class level and area of expertise
- 6. As far as the Turabian guide to academic writing is concerned, the two most common citation forms/styles are?**
- Bibliography style and the Author-Date style⁶**
- In-text and conclusion
- Bibliography and narrative statement
- Essay and research
- 7. Good academic writing depends on having useful sources. From the Turabian guide, identify three sources that can play a crucial role during research?**
- Primary, secondary and tertiary sources⁷**
- Low level, mid level and high level sources
- Simple, extra and advanced
- Secondary, college and primary
- 8. The aim of establishing the World Health Organization style guide as a house rule was to guide writers of research and other academic work. Its other function is?**
- House style to ensure consistency⁸**
- House style to add beauty to research

⁶ Turabian, 102.

⁷ Turabian, 24.

⁸ WHO, *Style Guide* (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2004), 1.

- House style rule to edit and fix errors
- House style to modify research topics

9. Some rules of good and sound academic writing would include?

- Citing, citing and citing
- Time and early submission
- Incorporating all the aspects taught and learned
- Stating main thesis, staying focused and writing clearly⁹**

10. Easy writing is an art that needs more time and attention to detail. However, it requires two types of thinking, namely?

- Logic and summary
- Typing and reading
- Creative and Critical¹⁰**
- Visionary and interpretation.

⁹ EUCLID, 2-4.

¹⁰ Ibid., 2.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
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